

Open Science Principles for the ENLIGHT European University Alliance

Funded by the Horizon 2020
programme of the EU
Grant agreement No 101035819

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Context and Aim

ENLIGHT, an alliance of ten comprehensive research-intensive universities, engages in a fundamental education transformation and works towards a joint research and innovation agenda. Core to ENLIGHT's mission is to address today's societal and environmental challenges and to work in partnership with the surrounding ecosystems by embracing and promoting practices that make scholarly research more open, collaborative, and responsive to societal changes.

ENLIGHT recognizes that Open Science, as an enabler of the quality and impact of research, entails a wide range of research and dissemination practices. ENLIGHT endorses the core values and guiding principles for implementing Open Science as expressed by the UNESCO Recommendations on Open Science (UNESCO, 2021).

Open Science is becoming increasingly important to make research processes and outputs accessible and reusable by all. ENLIGHT is committed to implementing an 'open by default' approach to online resources, for its teaching, research, outreach and engagement activities, for the benefit of science and society.

Open Science plays a key role in the ENLIGHT universities' higher education transformation agendas. It is a powerful driver for transparency, accountability and reusability in research and increases collaboration. Therefore it should be deeply embedded in the research processes and profiles of ENLIGHT researchers and institutions.

With this statement the ENLIGHT alliance would like to express its commitment to an Open Science culture that is guided by following general principles:

ENLIGHT Open Science principles:

1. Promotion of Open Science

The ENLIGHT alliance recognizes that Open Science is a key component of their scholarly processes. Therefore we

- Enhance the sharing of knowledge and good practices at the institutional level and across the ENLIGHT alliance.
- Aim to support Open Science broadly, including via training and skills development.
- Support the development and realization of an Open Science agenda and policy.

2. FAIR and Open Data

The ENLIGHT alliance stresses the importance of the FAIR data principles (**F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable) and will

- Support the implementation of FAIR, for example by developing or contributing to FAIR-enabling infrastructures, and/or by guiding researchers towards such existing infrastructures.
- Optimize access to research data and the use of such digital research data wherever possible (“as open as possible as close as necessary”).
- Work towards using and contributing to a distributed and open infrastructure for research data, including integration with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

3. Open Access

The ENLIGHT alliance underlines the value and benefits of unrestricted and immediate open access to scholarly publications and thus will

- Encourage and support researchers in providing free and unrestricted online access to all research publications, ideally immediately after publication.
- Promote bibliodiversity and increase awareness of various open access routes available as an alternative to author-pays models of open access.
- Support researchers in retaining their original rights to share and publish their works and other research outputs under an open license.

4. Open Education

The ENLIGHT alliance supports Open Education as a valuable part of a diverse and inclusive environment and will

- Encourage their research and teaching staff to create, share and use open educational materials and methodologies.
- Strive to support training and development opportunities for the research community that facilitate an understanding of open educational tools and methodologies.

5. Responsible Research Assessment

The ENLIGHT alliance promotes the inclusion of Open Science principles in research assessment and will

- Raise awareness for the different aspects of research assessment reform and commit to high quality standards in their own research assessment procedures.
- Align with the [Declaration on Research Assessment](#) (DORA) or the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) (CoARA), wherever possible.
- Incentivize Open Science practices as means for enhancing the quality and impact of research.

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Uppsala, 23 November 2023